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Abstract	Documentation of target specification of all relevant technical aspects of the MMA component, its sub-modules, their manufacture and corresponding assemblies. This plan shall guide all partners in their work on preparation and execution of individual tasks.
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Executive Summary

REALHOLO is a project to develop an advanced micro-mirror-based piston-type spatial light modulator (SLM) for real holographic 3D mixed reality (MR) display applications and active illumination. We will create this new type of SLM based on micro-mirror-array (MMA) technology for active modulation of the phase of visible light. Key advantages of its features shall be validated with selected application settings. The MMA's movable mirrors will be realized in micro-electrical-mechanical system (MEMS) technology.

After six months since the start of REALHOLO, first results were created in form of simulations, validated specifications, component and systems development plans and start of design and manufacturing activities.

This document provides an overview of the motivation and objectives of REALHOLO in combination with desired specifications and corresponding challenges. An outlook beyond REALHOLO is given with focus on opportunities arising from future availability of the new component and potential further steps to proper commercialization.

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Chapter 1 Introduction to REALHOLO

1.1 Motivation

Emerging mixed reality (MR) applications demand a natural visual experience with an increased depth range from touching distance to the horizon - without physiological side effects which are known from alternative and intermediate technologies such as stereoscopic 3D. The required natural visual experience can only be achieved with real holographic displays which have been principally demonstrated on the base of available component technologies - both for direct view (e.g. a LCD display) and projection (micro displays) spatial light modulators (SLMs).

REALHOLO will develop enabling solutions superior to prior art technologies such as plain 2D imaging or stereoscopic 3D and demonstrate the unique new capabilities and technology-inherent advantages of mirror-based modulation in their combination with real holography. In REALHOLO, the main objective is the development of a new type of SLM which is especially optimized for holographic image generation for MR applications.

Figure 1: Artist impression of the hologram generation on the base of the REALHOLO MMA-based SLM.

The application of this SLM will be demonstrated and validated in two use cases within REALHOLO. The first application will be a MR system, a head-up display (HUD), which will make use of the SLM's unique features. In a secondary use case demonstration, an active headlamp, we will evaluate the SLM's advantages for active illumination.

1.1.1 Prior-art mixed reality solutions

In typical prior-art MR devices, especially in HUDs, plain 2D images are projected into the user's sight at a single distance. This strongly reduces the freedom in the content that can be superimposed onto the real world. Another known approach, stereoscopic imaging, is an extension of this principle. Stereoscopic 3D displays show a different regular 2D image to the left and right eye of an observer separated by 3D glasses or by optics in the displays. This does not create real 3D but only two times 2D. Stereoscopic 3D systems show images on fixed planes which mean that the eyes can only focus there while the virtual objects are displayed at different depths. This leads to physiological side effects like eye fatigue, misjudgement, motion sickness and accommodation-vergence conflict¹. Missing relative depth between virtual objects also prohibits motion parallax. As result, only a subset of all natural visual cues to the human eyes are present which prohibits proper viewing.

Even more advanced stereoscopic 3D approaches as such light field (stereoscopic multi-view) are limited by inherent optical properties. Accordingly, light field may generate some motion parallax but at the cost of image resolution. 3D depth is limited to very little (Centimetres) range due to the refractive nature (and corresponding divergence) of such systems' illumination.¹

A large portion of the population cannot properly see stereo 3D and suffer from misperception of depth, headaches or worse. Accordingly, stereo 3D displays have to greatly reduce depth to reduce observer problems which also eliminates important features which motivated the effort in the first place, e.g. 3D depth must now be compressed, so it is not properly scaled anymore and therefore unsuitable for professional use and unattractive for consumer use. Currently available MR displays typically only show information in one plane with a very restricted user experience.^{2 3}

It is generally recognised that only real holography is capable of generating all natural visual cues and it can accordingly be seen as an enabling technology for strongly improved MR systems.

1.1.2 How to satisfy visual requirements of mixed reality solutions

Holography is often called the gold standard for MR products. While stereo 3D or simple refractive optics-based light field 3D has a small depth zone of comfort and high resolution, a real holographic MR display can, due to its non-limiting nature, integrate computed and interactive content with reality at all distances, from touching distance to the horizon. Only real holographic image generation properly generates true 3D content in space, properly positioned relative to real world objects, including all visual cues. This cannot just be seen with human eyes but also verified using regular cameras.

Generation of real holographic reconstructions (3D objects in space) is not based on regular imaging with pixels on 2D modulators (e.g. standard LCD). Real holography uses interference of light emanating from a pixel matrix, where pixels can individually control the phase (timing) of light. This can be done with liquid crystal materials (due to their polar birefringent nature) or with mirrors changing the light's path length. The latter approach will be followed in REALHOLO.

Proper real holographic image generation from interference of coherent light (phase modulation) allows^{IV}:

- The “ultimate” display, generating light with the same properties as from real natural objects — correctly perceived by the human physiology (eyes plus brain processing centres) — generated in space itself, not just on a flat physical or projected display
- 3D scenes with depth ranging (continuously) from touching distance all the way to the horizon
- Images of a very high and constant image resolution (exceeding that of the human retina) at any 3D scene depth
- Proper viewer eye focus within any 3D scene at will, even in a still projected hologram
- Interactive real-time capability at normal frame rates (in spite of bandwidth and computation requirements)
- A viewing experience as comfortable and true to nature as real life, without limitations in 3D scene depth or time comfortably spent in front of the display. No ambiguity from missing visual cues.

The following figure illustrates the principle of a holographic MR application of a head-up display (HUD) as we are planning to realize in REALHOLO.

Figure 2: Principle of a holographic HUD based on the REALHOLO SLM.

Digitally calculated hologram data will be written into the SLM and coherent illumination, different optical elements and the half-reflective wind shield will project the hologram into the observer’s sight of the street. The SLM’s active area will be magnified and projected at one distance into the space in front of the windscreen but it will not be directly visible, only the generated content will be holographically generated over a wide depth range.

Different options to hologram generation exist. REALHOLO will deploy the most efficient way which only generates the information visible to the observers’ eye (limited to eye boxes without losses from information invisible to eyes) and therefore becomes real-time capable and, combined with the new modulators, highly efficient, low noise and commercially feasible. The enabling elements to the solution are called “Sub-holograms” and “Viewing Windows” and had been proven and demonstrated by SeeReal before REALHOLO ^v. The sub-hologram technology does not only make hologram computation feasible with reasonable effort – it will also allows to simplify the SLM. With the sub-hologram technology, the required number of pixels can be strongly reduced compared to a classical hologram but still is larger than the number of pixels of typical prior-art SLMs. Furthermore, the sub-holograms relax the requirements on the laser’s coherence length.

The principle is illustrated in Figure 3. The left side of the figure shows a classical hologram where a huge number of pixels is required to generate a wide diffraction angle, which enables an unnecessarily wide viewing angle of the observer onto the scene. The right side of the figure shows the sub-hologram technology where the diffraction angle is strongly reduced such that it only covers a much smaller “viewing window”. The viewing window is steered onto the observers eye boxes in the optical system. The sub-hologram technology enables the utilization of SLMs with a much smaller number of pixels and strongly reduces computation effort because for each point of the scene, sub-holograms needs to be calculated which cover only a small fraction of the SLM’s area. All sub-holograms of the complete scene need to be superpositioned and then written into the SLM.

Figure 3: REALHOLO hologram generation principle using sub-holograms.

The advances of today's semiconductor industries enable real holography for computational content. Advanced, newly developed MEMS technologies allow fast modulating MMA's for a precise phase modulation with a large number of pixels. Advanced CMOS nodes allow hologram generation with low power consumption and production cost. In REALHOLO, we will take advantage of these technological developments.

1.1.3 Principle of the REALHOLO SLM

The spatial light modulator (SLM) of first generation real holographic projection prototype set-ups is usually based on liquid crystal (LC) display technology which is the limiting factor on the performance as will be described in the next section. In REALHOLO we will develop a new type of SLM, a micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) based reflective micro-display: a micro mirror array (MMA) component with a unique set of properties which is especially suited for real holographic MR displays but also for many other applications from high value to high volume.

The principle of a reflective phase-modulating SLM on the base of mirror arrays is sketched in the following figure.

Figure 4: Illustration of the phase modulating principle of the MMA.

Coherent illumination (here from top left) is reflected at different altitude when the stroke of the mirror is changed. This results in phase differences between pixels, depending on their individual deflection. This MMA principle enables projection holography.

An adjustment of the vertical deflection of the individual mirrors of a large micro-mirror array (MMA) allows, together with a coherent illumination, a holographic image generation. The illustrated spring-force system is created in MEMS technology and the force is built up by voltages that are generated directly on the CMOS chip that is forming the base for building up the MEMS structures. More details can be found in the following Chapter 2.

1.1.4 Requirements on the SLM and the advantages of mirror arrays

From the holographic application's point of view, there are a few main requirements on the SLM to be fulfilled.

First-of-all, for a good perceived quality of the hologram, a large number of pixels are beneficial. In an liquid crystal pixel, the optical properties are strongly changing in the area close to the border of each pixel due to electrical fields from neighbouring pixels^{vi vii}. These effects have a very large impact when the pixels are shrunk further which is in turn necessary for reaching a large number of pixels. In comparison, a mirror array inherently offers much higher phase quality within the individual pixels due to the rigid surface of the mirrors. The challenge is to minimize differences in the mirror surface between pixels and to minimize tilting of mirrors.

Second-of-all, for a good perceived quality of the hologram, the phase modulation of the individual pixels, which is directly related to the vertical deflection of individual mirrors in an MMA, must be adjusted in a "near-analogue" large number of steps over the required range of at least 2π and the range of wavelengths.

Third-of-all, for MR holographic displays require a high-speed SLM because multiple holograms, at least one hologram for each color and for each eye, need to be displayed time-sequentially to the observer. Accordingly, for one observer a full-colored holographic scene must be at least driven by a SLM that has a six times higher framerate than the scene itself. For example, an update rate of 540Hz is required on the SLM to show a scene at 90Hz. Within the update period of the SLM, the contents need to be electrically updated, settle and illumination must take place.

A typically planned time sequence for the REALHOLO in an MR application is illustrated in Figure 5. Each color's hologram is written to the matrix and then illuminated separately. During the time of writing, the voltages are updated row-by-row and then, after the voltages of all mirrors have been updated and the mirrors have settled to the new deflection, the coherent illumination will generate the respective color's holographic scene.

Figure 5: Typical sequence of operation of the SLM

Such speeds can not be easily reached for liquid-crystal based 2π phase-modulating SLMs. Fast available near-analogue-precision phase-modulating LCOS reach adaptation times of the liquid crystal in the few-milliseconds range^{VIII} which is more than two orders of magnitude slower than the mirror settling time that can be reached in MMA-based SLMs. Micro mirrors can move much quicker from one stroke to another than a volume of liquid crystal can align to a new state.

1.2 Objectives of the REALHOLO project

Principle considerations about the objectives, potential solutions and technological requirements for the new device and corresponding selected key fields of applications were investigated by founding members of the REALHOLO consortium prior to this application and for some time. The consortium partners have assessed the objectives as ambitious but achievable, given the significant expertise, experience and commercial commitment already proven before this project.

1.2.1 Key target properties of the REALHOLO SLM

In the following table, some key features of the SLM are summarized which are fulfilling the above named requirements on pixel count, phase resolution and speed for a good performance in MR applications.

Parameter	Value	Details
mirror count	4000 by 2400	9.6 million mirrors
mirror size	4 μm by 6 μm	
frame rate	> 1 kHz	
deflection range	0 ... 350 nm	for $>2\pi$ modulation of visible light
deflection precision	8 bit	(~ 0.9 nm steps for blue light)
mirror tilt	< 0.1°	
mirror settling time	5 ... 10 μs	
variants of the SLM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> phase-modulating variant complex-valued variant with mounted beam combiner 	The variants will be created by either placing a simple cover glass or the beam combiner, see chapter 2.

Table 1: Key SLM specifications

More details on the technical realization of the SLM are given in Chapter 2.

1.2.2 Key target properties of the primary use case demonstration of head-up display

Within REALHOLO, a prototype of a head-up display will be built on the base of the new SLM. This will be used to create a head-up display that allows to display contents over a wide range of distance from the driver. Holographic 3D image generation for automotive use aims to enable super-positioning of virtual objects with real life objects or environments. One example may be navigational symbols properly positioned in real space. Accordingly, a turn arrow should be placed many meters away at the intersection where the turn is supposed to take place. The navigational symbol of the grocery store should be placed right where the store is located. And the symbol warning about a crossing pedestrian should be only a few meters away. Therefore, the 3D range ability of the REALHOLO holographic HUD demonstrator will be from near 2.5m to far away 50-100m which can be extended in the future. Image resolution should be similar to what users experience in other displays. The term Full HD has become commonplace but in fact it was aimed at typical human eye resolution. So a Full HD TV at home, properly placed, generates about the resolution where one cannot really resolve individual pixels anymore. Images appear smooth. In optics terms this corresponds to 1 arc minute, which in turn is 60 pixels per 1° field-of-view (FOV), i.e. 60 pixels-per-degree (ppd). REALHOLO resolution is aimed at 70 ppd, i.e. even higher than average eyesight ability and in turn generates smooth images without jagged edges.

Automotive HUD have become more popular over the past years. While early HUD systems provided the driver with a field of view (FOV) of about 3°, more recently this was expanded to about 5°, introduced in upper and mid-range cars but starting to filtering down to more compact models. Latest higher-end HUDs deliver even more than 10° FOV. Corresponding optical systems scale up to over 20 litres of volume as result of the inherent physics^{ix}. Still, targets for future HUD range up to 15 or some even beyond 20° FOV. This is typically also translated in how many highway lanes a virtual image may cover, where 3 lanes in a not too far distance are desirable. Since such very large FOV systems, with today's optical solutions, require immense system volumes, they have not become generally accepted roadmap items. The improved abilities of the REALHOLO MEMS-based SLM, especially the high frame rate which could enable tiling scenarios, are expected to facilitate new concepts formerly not thought possible.

The configuration of the SLM component to be developed in REALHOLO allows real holographic HUD configurations of ~10° and higher in straight forward system configurations, i.e. without tiling or scanning. So its core specifications are already directly suitable for future HUD product developments. Nonetheless, due to key objectives of REALHOLO and corresponding milestone budgets, use case validations focus on key USP (unique selling points/features) enabled by holographic applications based on the new device. Accordingly, the HUD setup will focus on holographic USP (as 3D depth range, 3D depth resolution) and typical quality features of projection systems (as background contrast, image resolution) and not on rather classical optics challenges (as maximum FOV or maximum brightness).

Besides the specifications of the SLM itself, real-time hologram computation is needed for a final MR product and therefore, some effort will be spent in REALHOLO on adapting hologram algorithms to the system.

Key specifications are summarized in the table below and more details are given in Chapter 3.

Parameter	Value
Depth range of content	2.5 ... 100 m
Angular resolution anywhere in 3D depth	70 ppd (pixels-per-degree)
Field-of-view	8° by 4°

Table 2: Key HUD specifications

1.2.3 Key target properties of the secondary use case demonstration of an active headlamp

The second demonstrated use case of the REALHOLO SLM will be that of an active headlamp. The holographic approach will here be used to optimize the efficiency of the SLM from light source to the projection. In order to demonstrate and validate the principal advantage of holographic light field generation combined with the ability to redistribute light by phase modulation and interference, structured illumination shall be done for a potential active automotive headlamp.

In autonomous driving, cars may “communicate” with pedestrians to convey and establish confidence in the actions of the vehicle (e.g. “I really stopped”) or provide information about the environment (e.g. “Careful, something is passing behind me. Don’t cross”). A certain range of projections, e.g. of symbols on the road, could be envisaged as possible solution.

While symbolic information on the tarmac in front of a vehicle can be much simpler than for instance typical high-resolution LCD, the same quality parameters can be used, e.g. contrast and resolution. In an active headlamp, recognition of information is key, not fidelity of grey scales. In order for an observer to be able to distinguish displayed (projected) information on a surface, a minimum relative brightness difference to this background is required. These numbers are surprisingly low but already well known from other applications. For a long time displays of mobile phones or desk calculators were quite simple; contrast was well below 1:50, often below 1:10. Still information was very well legible. As long as spatial resolution of an image matches physiological perception, even a contrast as low as 1:2 is legible. Also large objects on plain background are easier to recognize than more complex images on a cluttered background. Similar applies to resolution of such symbols. For instance, a large “Stop” sign of 1m diameter projected on the tarmac could be compiled of laterally 100 or so pixels and still be perceived as very high resolution; in pixels per inch this would still only be about 3-5 ppi .

In the validation example of an active headlamp we target an image resolution of 5 ppi and a contrast of at least 1:10.

The active part of a holographic headlamp would always be in addition to the actual road illumination function. Also the illumination region of the active part will be smaller and more targeted. Still, it is expected that such active functionality would mostly be applicable during off-daylight hours because even on a cloudy day sunlight is more than a typical headlamp can overcome (no shadows on the tarmac from headlamp at daytime).

Similar to the use case validation approach for automotive HUD, the setup for structured illumination will also focus on the ability to redistribute light and sending it to desired regions of an image plane instead of blocking it in the modulator, i.e. improved efficiency. Classic optical challenges as maximum brightness or largest possible FOV will not be focus of this validation. The key specifications for the headlamp can be found in the table below.

Because the light is redistributed in the phase-only modulating variant of the SLM, the brightness scales with the area of the symbol that is shown. This shows a main advantage of phase-modulating holographic approach compared to amplitude-modulating LC-displays or the Texas Instruments DMD binary MMA technology. In these cases, the light is absorbed in places that should not be lit and the efficiency of the display is decreasing with smaller area of the symbols that are shown. Technologies like LED arrays or scanning mirrors can be more efficient compared to amplitude-modulating displays because only part of the pixels (LED array) are switched on or only for part of the time (scanning mirror) the light source is on and no light is absorbed or blocked. But still, the maximum brightness is limited by the brightness of the single LED or the scanner light source. The advantage of the phase-only SLM is that light from the whole SLM area can be redistributed and concentrated to small symbols. That means those symbols can be brighter than the illuminated SLM pixels. A phase-only LCOS could also be utilized in a holographic set-up but here, illumination must take place with only a single polarization state. Then only free-beam illumination with a laser source avoids losses but more convenient ways - like for example multi-mode-fiber based laser illumination or use of other light sources leads to losses in the efficiency due to required polarization filters. For a phase-only variant of the SLM, the phase modulation is independent of the polarization state which eases illumination and leads to higher efficiency compared to an LCOS.

The SLM is not primarily optimized for this use case and the purpose of the demo is to investigate this path and prepare a development of a later refined specialized variant of the SLM. The demo will be based on the phase-modulating variant of the SLM because of its larger efficiency. More details can be found in Chapter 3.

Parameter	Value	Details
Content-independent efficiency of flux source-to-road	25%	
Field-of-illumination	1.5 m by 2 ... 4 m	good symbol size within lane
Angular resolution on road	5 pixels-per-inch	
Laser source power	2 W for each laser (R,G,B)	In demo, can be optimized in commercialization
Large-area brightness	150 lx	for a 1 m ² symbol with above listed laser source power
Peak brightness	10000 lx	for a 10x10 cm ² symbol with above listed laser source power

Table 3: Key headlamp specifications

It should be mentioned that there are many more applications for structured illumination where dynamic wave-field modulation with good contrast and image fidelity is of great advantage and absolute maximum brightness is of lesser concern.

Chapter 2 Realization of the SLM

Real holography works with coherent light. It is therefore not possible to use individual light sources for each pixel of a display, like for example in OLED displays. Instead, the light from a common sufficiently coherent light source has to be modulated spatially (pixel by pixel), and also temporally (frame by frame). The key component of a real holographic display is therefore a spatial light modulator (SLM). For projection holography, a reflective micro display is the preferred choice. As explained in Chapter 1, real holography calls for SLMs that modulate the phase of an incoming coherent wave front of light with many millions of pixels at kHz frame rates. The image is formed by diffraction (interference of light from multiple pixels). Ideally, the phase modulation would be analogue, but a digital approximation with a precision of 8 bit is sufficient. Binary addressing of the pixels, as done in some prior art MEMS, does impose unacceptable issues for real holographic displays.

Up to now, most attempts at real holographic displays use liquid crystal on silicon (LCoS) SLMs. Most prior art attempts use holographic principles to only generate flat 2D projections/images but with the increased efficiency of holographic/phase modulation. While this may work in principle, LCoS SLMs have rather limited frame rates and show quite a large crosstalk of neighbouring pixels. The phase within a single pixel is not very uniform but will instead have an unwanted transition region at the pixel edges that for small pixels may span almost the whole pixel. These inherent drawbacks of the LC principle in small pixels can be overcome by micro mirror arrays (MMA). MMAs are capable of kHz frame rates instead of around 60-400Hz for LCoS, optical cross talk can be eliminated and electrical crosstalk can be extremely small if the pixel is designed properly. The variation of the phase modulation within a single pixel depends only on the micro mirror planarity and can be negligible compared to the modulation range.

The key specifications of the SLM are listed in Table 1. The SLM consists of three main parts that are described in more detail below, following the order of the actual built up of the SLM:

1. The backplane, a mixed-signal CMOS integrated circuit die, is forming the base of the SLM. It is receiving the hologram data and generates the voltages for the individual mirrors.
2. The MMA's mirrors are realized as micro-electro-mechanical-system (MEMS). The array is built on top of the backplane with individual electrodes for each mirror.
3. The SLM is packaged for the purpose of mechanically fixing, electrically and thermally contacting the backplane, protection and guaranteeing the required optical quality. During this process, the base SLM (which is only modulating the phase of the light), is planned to be converted into a complex-modulating SLM for a part of the SLMs by mounting a passive optical element, the "beam combiner".

2.1 CMOS backplane

The purpose of the CMOS backplane is to receive the digital hologram data during a phase of writing, to perform digital-to-analogue conversion and then drive the pixels in active-matrix-like row-by-row writing scheme and to realize the matrix of addressable storage capacitors and connect them to the MMA.

A simple sketch of the planned CMOS backplane can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Block diagram of the main REALHOLO CMOS backplane functions.

Naturally, the actual matrix will be of the same size as the mirror array and accordingly, the die size will be larger than the active area, the current estimate is about a square of 2 cm size.

The main challenges in realizing the backplane are the large bandwidth, which is a result of the limited writing time and the large amount of hologram data, and the target precision of 10bit in the voltage domain.

The CMOS design is conducted by REALHOLO partners nSilition and omniChip. The manufacturing will be done by REALHOLO partner X-FAB in the process XH018, resulting in fabricated wafer lots with fully functional backplanes for the future micro-displays.

In addition, to prepare for the industrialization in the markets having stringent quality requirements, the used digital libraries will be guaranteed as zero-dppm (zero-defective part per million) i.e. all potential manufacturing defects are screened out during wafer test by reducing defect occurrence thanks to Design For Manufacturing technics and increasing the defect detectability by using state-of-the-art test methodology.

2.2 MEMS structured micro-mirror-array

The MMA's mirrors are the core technology of the SLM. They are realized as micro-electro-mechanical-systems (MEMS). The respective fabrication technology and the actuator design are developed by REALHOLO partner Fraunhofer IPMS.

The basic concepts for this have already been worked out by IPMS and SeeReal in previous studies. It was found that classical parallel-plate actuators ^X used in known MMAs may not be feasible for this task. Drawbacks of such prior art mirror-based attempts, especially high stroke precision and tilt avoidance with densely packed small pixels, can be overcome by a new comb-drive actuator ^{XI XII XIII}, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: Improved comb drive actuator for tilt-minimized and precise mirror movement.

The cyan part is the fixed stator electrode, the magenta its moving actuator counterpart. The double hinges which act as springs are shown in grey and the mirror is transparently shown on top.

With this concept, there is no pull-in in the stroke direction as would be the case for the parallel-plate actuators usually used in MMAs. Therefore, the electrodes can be much closer to each other, here in the order of 200 nm compared to about $2\mu\text{m}$ for a parallel-plate actuator. Much higher actuator forces can thus be generated in spite of the reduced electrode area. With fabrication parameters optimized for the desired stroke, the response curve can be quite close to linear, see Figure 8, so the precision requirement for the addressing voltage is manageable. Furthermore, the electrical fields are concentrated locally within the individual pixel and so crosstalk-effects, which can tilt a mirror or change its height due to the fields of neighbouring pixels, can be minimized.

Figure 8: a comb drive actuator has a response curve much closer to linear than the parallel plate actuators. Both response curves here are scaled to the same deflection range, which means much weaker hinges for the parallel plate case.

The novel comb-drive micro actuator array and micro mirrors will be fabricated in an surface-micro machining process that will be developed and optimized for this purpose. During the process 5 structural layers will be deposited and etched to the desired shapes. In between these, sacrificial layers are deposited and polished to enable the deposition of the next structural layer. The uppermost structural layer is the micro mirrors, where the planarity is of course of highest importance. In a final process step all the sacrificial layer material is removed by a selective gas-phase etch, so that the structural layers remain and are free to move in response to the addressing voltage.

2.3 Principle package concept

The purpose of the package is to

1. mechanically hold the SLM stable within the package and the whole system over life time and temperature variations
2. electrically connect the up to 500 pins of the CMOS backplane to the system level electronics
3. provide protection against environmental influences
4. provide a distortion-less optical path and allow the precise mounting of the beam combiner to create the complex-valued variant of the SLM

The SLM's package is sketched in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9: Sketch of the planned package.

The electrical connection will be achieved by a package substrate printed circuit board for contacting the driving electronics to the bond wires towards the MMA chip. The beam combiner will, for realization of the complex-modulating variant of the SLM - see next section, be mounted directly on the die and the whole structure will be encapsulated by a cost-effective plastic moulded package. The package and the whole backend process, including wafer and die handling and assembly of the individual parts of the package to the complete SLM, will be developed and realized by REALHOLO partners Sencio and Fraunhofer IPMS.

2.4 Complex-modulating variant of the SLM

The advantage of the complex-modulating approach is that the computation of the hologram can be simplified at the cost of efficiency and a more complex optical system and backend process. It is therefore an interesting variant of the device for MR applications that require “live” computer-generated holograms^{XIV}.

The complex-modulating variant of the SLM is based on the same die as the basic phase-only variant of the SLM. It is created by placing a passive optical element, the “beam combiner” on the die. The purpose of the beam combiner is to superimpose the reflected light of pairs of adjacent mirrors to complex-valued superpixels.

The beam combiner consists of two parts, a patterned retarder and a birefringent crystal. The structured retarder consists of alternating stripes of optically isotropic material and quarter-wave plates which change the polarization of the reflected light beam. The changed polarization of every second row causes, in combination with the birefringent crystal, a vertical displacement by one row of mirrors. Because each other row of the structured retarder consists of optically isotropic material, which does not change the polarization, the reflected light of each pair of vertical neighbouring mirrors is superimposed and can thus interfere. This allows a complex modulation of the light, meaning that both the phase and the amplitude of this complex-valued superpixel can be individually adjusted.

The layout of the two variants of the SLM are sketched in the figure below.

Figure 10: Basic layout of the two variants of the SLM.

In the left of the figure, the base phase-modulating variant of the SLM is shown. On the right, the complex-modulating variant of the SLM is shown which is created by mounting the beam combiner on top of the base SLM. The CMOS backplane and MEMS structures are identical for both variants. For a holographic MR system, both variants of the SLM have their advantages and accordingly, both will be validated for their utilization in the HUD demonstration.

Chapter 3 Realization of the use case validation

In REALHOLO, not only the SLM will be developed, but also possible applications will be evaluated. The first application will be a MR system, a head-up display (HUD), which will make use of the SLM's unique features. In a secondary use case demonstration, an active headlamp, we will evaluate the SLM's advantages for active illumination.

Both demonstrated use cases have different requirements on the SLM properties and its driving.

3.1 Hologram computation

In MR, a “live” display of the content at sufficiently low latency is required. For holographic MR this typically means that the hologram computation must be also solved with sufficiently short duration. Accordingly, for economically efficient system costs, the required computation effort is of large importance for holographic MR systems.

A hologram is usually calculated in the following steps:

1. A complex-valued pixel map is determined that describes the wave front of the perceived scene.
2. This needs to be transferred to the wave front at the SLM's location within the optical path, adapted to the SLM's modulation capabilities and converted into the SLM's data format.

For the simplification of the first step, the “sub-hologram” approach, see Figure 3, will be followed in REALHOLO. This relaxes the requirements on the number of pixels on the SLM and the computational load.

In case of a complex-modulating SLM, the second computation step can be quite simple, requiring only a simple data conversion, or might involve a single Fourier transform for mapping the complex-valued pixel map to the SLM's optical plane.

In case of a SLM that only modulates the phase of light, the second step is not as straightforward. The state-of-the-art approach of phase-only holographic encoding is using iterative algorithms like Gerchberg-Saxton^{XV}, which involve multiple Fourier transforms which are power- and time consuming. For real-time displays, this is a drawback.

For the headlamp use case demonstration, the real-time computation is not a major requirement and therefore we might rely on pre-computed holograms. For the headlamp, the phase-only variant of the SLM will be utilized because of its simplicity and light efficiency.

For the HUD demo, we will investigate the performance of both variants of the SLM and REALHOLO partner SeeReal will put some research effort on adapting alternative hologram algorithms to a realtime-capable solution with the phase-only variant of the SLM. For this purpose, within REALHOLO we plan to drive the SLM with an evolution of hologram computing algorithms.

3.2 Driving electronics

Within REALHOLO, partner omniChip will develop driving electronics that will be capable of

- Driving the SLM for
 - development purposes
 - during characterization
 - use-case evaluation
- The electronics will be capable of
 - Receiving high-bandwidth hologram data from the PC and buffering them
 - Conversion of the phase-value to the input data format and corrections on the data stream.
 - Sending the high-bandwidth hologram data stream to the SLM during the timing phase.
 - Allow synchronous control of other optical elements in the systems which will be especially used in the use case demos.

- Furthermore, the electronics might be used to conduct parts of the hologram computation.

3.3 Use case validation – Automotive HUD systems

The MMA is the key enabling element for real holographic projection systems that are compact, energy efficient and have unique imaging features and quality - impossible with today's state-of-the-art. REALHOLO will demonstrate its developments in a real holographic MR application implemented as a head-up display (HUD) prototype setup, potentially used with future vehicles.

Figure 11: Artist impression of a MR HUD for automotive use

The demonstrator display setup will, among custom designs using a mix of standard and proprietary optical and electronic components available to the project partners, also include a custom electronics solution for real-time hologram synthesis in a unique and convincing real holographic MR demonstration. Preparation of use case validation will be done concurrently with development and manufacture of functional MMA components. A HUD demonstrator will be built and characterized with subsequent evaluation of selected features.

A simplified sketch of a HUD setup is shown in Figure 2 and key specifications are listed in Table 2.

Both variants of the SLM will be evaluated for the HUD demo. As mentioned above, both have their advantages and it will be part of the project to evaluate which may be better suited for HUD.

The HUD use case will be developed and evaluated by REALHOLO partners Valeo and SeeReal.

3.4 Use case validation – Structured illumination in active headlamps

Phase of light modulation enables real holographic 3D display technology but more generally can be characterized by its ability to redistributing light within an illuminated area defined by the optical system. This enables improved energy efficiency when modulating light but also generates an opportunity of using actively structured illumination for various purposes. These range from small scale variable illumination of scientific samples (e.g. in bio-medical applications) to high-power active illumination in automotive headlamps for driver or pedestrian information.

Potential active illumination systems for automotive use in active headlamps enable the projection of information on the street or to steer or form the shape of the beam otherwise. Comparable state-of-the-art amplitude-modulating systems used for the same purpose may exhibit lower optical

efficiency and corresponding issues with power consumption and temperature management. Present liquid crystal-based modulators exhibit temperature-dependent performance with impact on achievable contrast as well as limited modulation speed.

Figure 12: Prior-art prototype system^{XVI} based on a binary micro-mirror DMD device

Preparation of active illumination use case validation will also be done concurrently with component development and manufacture.

As mentioned above, only the phase-modulating variant of the SLM will be used in the headlamp system because of its better efficiency. The optimization of efficiency is the primary goal for this demonstration and real-time computation is secondary, so we might rely on precomputed holograms.

The headlamp use case will be developed and evaluated by REALHOLO partner SeeReal.

Chapter 4 Summary and Outlook

REALHOLO paves the way towards new generations of mixed reality (MR) displays and therefore enables or greatly improves a wide variation of further optical applications in industry, science, security or the consumer space. This will be achieved with real holographic techniques to provide the best possible experience for the user without physiological side effects like eye fatigue, misjudgement, motion sickness and accommodation-vergence conflict, which are known from alternative and intermediate technologies such as stereoscopic 3D. The required natural visual experience can only be achieved with real holographic displays which have been principally demonstrated on the basis of available component technologies.

REALHOLO will develop a new type of SLM which is especially optimized for real holographic MR applications, a micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) based reflective micro-display: a micro mirror array (MMA) component with a unique set of properties.

The newly developed MEMS technology and MMA will be especially suited for real holographic MR displays but also many other applications from high value to high volume will benefit from the fast MMA's precise phase modulation with a large number of pixels. The SLM will be developed to a near-prototype state.

Its utilization will be demonstrated primarily in a MR application, namely a real holographic head-up display with a large range of depth of the displayed content, and a structured light application, an light -efficient active headlamp for e.g. communication of an autonomous vehicle.

The development is conducted by eight partners from six different countries with multi-disciplinary expertise, especially MEMS and semiconductor technologies, electronic design, holographic, optical design and application-specific expertise.

Chapter 5 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor
FOV	Field-of-view
HUD	Head-up display
LC	Liquid crystal
LCD	Liquid crystal display - transparent for direct view with a backlight
LCoS	Liquid crystal on silicon - reflective microdisplay for projection
MEMS	Micro-electro-mechanical system
MMA	Micro-mirror-array
MR	Mixed-reality
PC	Personal Computer
SLM	Spatial light modulator

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